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Quantification and mapping of tyre wear emissions: from EU regional analysis to global projections

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ABSTRACT

Tyre wear particle (TWP) emissions are a major source of microplastic pollution. This study analyzes the variability in national TWP emissions estimated through different methodologies and provides guidance for optimizing these estimations. Findings show substantial discrepancies in per capita emissions across European countries, with variations up to 2 kg/y*cap, particularly between Southern and Eastern European countries, as well as Estonia and Finland. In contrast, Western European countries exhibit minimal variation despite diverse methodologies. We predicted annual TWP loads reaching environmental compartments such as air, soil, sewers, and surface waters. Germany, France, and Italy were identified as major emitters, each exceeding 100,000 tons annually. Notably, only a small fraction of these emissions, approximately 13,000 tons per year, reaches surface waters due to varying efficiencies of wastewater treatment facilities. Based on the country-specific emission estimates, we developed predictive models for emission estimation based on socioeconomic variables such as Gross Domestic Product. While a simplified Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) model identified key linear drivers, a more advanced Random Forest (RF) model demonstrated significantly higher predictive accuracy (LOOCV $R^2 > 0.7$ for major vehicle types), revealing the complex, non-linear nature of emission drivers. This dual-modeling approach provides a robust framework for global projections, highlighting Luxembourg and the United States as leaders in per capita emissions (3.56 and 3.12 kg/cap*y, respectively), while China and India exhibit the highest total emissions. Our predictive models reduce data requirements and facilitate a preliminary, data-driven estimation of the global distribution of TWP emissions.

1. Introduction

Global plastic production, currently estimated at 435 million tons, is expected to reach 736 million tons by 2040 (OECD, 2024). Plastics, valued for being lightweight and durable (Hale et al., 2022), are essential in various daily products from packaging (Mason et al., 2018) and cosmetics (Napper et al., 2015) to textiles (Napper and Thompson, 2016) and automotive tyres (Kole et al., 2017). However, their introduction into the environment leads to paradoxical effects: the durable nature of plastics causes them to degrade slowly and incompletely, potentially persisting for up to 2500 years and generating microplastic fragments (Schwarz et al., 2023; Chamas et al., 2020). Among all degraded plastic fragments, microplastics, i.e., plastic particles <5 mm (Cózar et al., 2014), have emerged as a significant global environmental threat (Blettler et al., 2018).

Tyre wear particles (TWP) are a significant source of microplastic

pollution, primarily formed through friction between tyre treads and road surfaces (Wagner et al., 2018; Boucher et al., 2020; Knight et al., 2020). Recent EU-wide inventories have revealed that approximately 94,000 tonnes per year of TWP enter European surface waters, accounting for 53 % of all primary microplastics discharged into these systems. In comparison, polymer pellets and laundering fibers contribute only 22 % (41,000 t/y) and 7 % (13,000 t/y), respectively (Hann et al., 2016). The typical tyre composition consists of carbon black, metals, fibers, and chemical additives, with nearly half of the tyre made up of a mix of natural and synthetic rubbers (Sommer et al., 2018). This interaction not only results in TWP but also in a complex mixture of road wear and mineral dust, collectively referred to as Tyre and Road Wear Particles (TRWP) (Baensch-Baltruschat et al., 2021). For the purpose of this study, we focus specifically on TWP, separating the tyre-derived fraction of TRWP due to its significant contribution to microplastic pollution (Mennekes and Nowack, 2022; Sommer et al., 2018;

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Wagner et al., 2018). These particles are containing hazardous additives and heavy metals, posing established risks to both aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems (Ding et al., 2023; Halle et al., 2020; Wagner et al., 2018).

The environmental hazards associated with tyre wear underscore the critical question of the actual magnitude of TWP emissions and their distribution across various environmental compartments. Although numerous studies have aimed to quantify national tyre wear emissions, they face considerable challenges due to methodological diversity. Various approaches, such as those based on mass loss (Hillenbrand et al., 2005), tyre thickness loss (Yamashita and Yamanaka, 2013), and emission factors (Baensch-Baltruschat et al., 2020), rely on distinct assumptions and data inputs. This results in inconsistent outcomes even for the same geographical locations (Kole et al., 2017), with an absence of standardized guidelines for selecting the most appropriate estimation method under specific conditions.

The challenge is further compounded by the use of different metrics to represent annual tyre wear emissions—namely TWP, TRWP, and Rubber. For instance, TWP accounts for approximately 75 % of the total TRWP material (Mian et al., 2022), and Rubber represents about half of the total TWP (Sommer et al., 2018). The lack of uniform metrics can lead to substantial discrepancies; using TRWP as the measurement could result in estimates roughly 2.7 times higher than those calculated when using Rubber, complicating both the comparison across studies and the validation of emission models.

Furthermore, the majority of empirical and estimative studies on TWP emissions are disproportionately concentrated in developed regions, specifically Western and Northern Europe. This regional focus has created significant gaps in global emission data, particularly from developing countries. For instance, early assessments in Norway and Denmark offered initial estimates based on primary emission factors applicable mostly to local vehicle types, resulting in Norway's annual emissions being estimated at approximately 4500 tons and Denmark's at 7660 tons (Sundt et al., 2014; Lassen et al., 2015). Subsequent studies, like those conducted in the Netherlands, have broadened the scope by including a wider range of vehicle and road types, leading to more comprehensive and refined estimates (Quik et al., 2025), where annual TWP emissions were 12,500 tons. The lack of data from non-European regions severely restricts the ability to compile a global perspective on TWP emissions. This limitation not only narrows the understanding of TWP's environmental impacts globally but also hinders the development of international mitigation strategies. Addressing this disparity is crucial for forming effective global environmental policies and for increasing awareness in regions that are currently underrepresented in TWP research.

This study aims to provide a comprehensive, multi-layered assessment of TWP emissions. First, we estimate and compare annual TWP emissions across EU member states using three distinct methodologies, offering guidance on optimizing national-level estimates and quantifying their inherent uncertainties. We then assess the distribution of these emissions into key environmental compartments, including the fraction reaching surface waters. Moving beyond estimation, the core of this study is the development and comparison of a dual-predictive modeling framework. We begin by constructing an interpretable Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) model to identify key linear relationships between emissions and socioeconomic indicators like Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Subsequently, to capture the real-world complexity, we develop a high-performance Random Forest (RF) machine learning model. By comparing these models, we not only create a scalable tool for global projections but also reveal the fundamentally non-linear nature of TWP emission drivers. The application of our RF model provides a global emission map, highlighting potential hotspots in data-scarce regions. This global assessment aims to stimulate targeted empirical research and inform the development of more nuanced, evidence-based environmental policies worldwide.

2. Methods

The following subsection describes how the methodologies and data were identified and extracted from public literature. We subsequently describe three methods for estimating TWP emissions at the national level, including the associated input parameters. Finally, the pathways of TWP to different environmental compartments are described, as well as the development of the emission prediction model and its performance evaluation.

2.1. Literature review

An extensive literature search was conducted using “Web of Science” and “Google Scholar” to gather literature on quantifying TWP emissions, as well as essential data on emission factors (EFs) and tyre wear loss rates. The data collection cutoff was August 2023 and primary keywords used were “Tire”, “Tyre”, “Tire wear”, and “Tyre wear”, in combination with other keywords such as “Microplastic”, “WWTP”, “Soil” and “Surface Water” to limit the search scope. Additionally, to establish the prediction model, further keywords including “multiple linear regression model”, “prediction”, “observable characteristics”, and “dependencies” were used to identify potential determinants. In addition to the scientific articles and review papers retrieved from the aforementioned databases, internet search engines (specifically Google) were utilized to identify grey publications and reports published by branch and research organizations using the stated keywords. Following the retrieval of these documents, a preliminary screening was carried out, involving a scan of the abstracts to ascertain the relevance of each publication. If a paper was judged relevant for the objectives of our study, it was reviewed in detail. At this stage, methodologies and data for estimating TWP emissions were extracted and systematically cataloged.

2.2. Methods to estimate TWP emissions

2.2.1. Method 1 (Weight loss)

The first technique for estimating annual TWP emissions is based on (1) the total number of registrations for all vehicle categories nationwide, (2) the weight of tyres for different vehicle types, and (3) the average weight loss of these tyres during their usage phase:

$$E_1 = \sum_{i=1}^n N_{\text{tyre},i} \times W_{\text{tyre},i} \times L_{\text{mass}} (n = 1 \dots 5) \quad (1)$$

where E_1 = the yearly country-based TWP emission using method 1 (kg/year); i = index parameter to identify the vehicle category for which the TWP emission is estimated (i.e., passenger cars, light commercial vehicles, heavy-duty vehicles, buses, and mopeds) (-); $N_{\text{tyre},i}$ = the total number of tyres for each vehicle type registered in a country (-); $W_{\text{tyre},i}$ = the weight of tyres for each vehicle type (kg); L_{mass} = the annual weight loss rate of the tyres, with a range between 2.5 % and 7.5 % (%/year).

Table S1 lists the broad range of weight losses ($L_{\text{tyre},i}$) reported in literature. For the purposes of this study, a weight loss range of 10 %-30 % was adopted. Considering the typical lifespan of a tyre varies by vehicle type, passenger cars and light commercial vehicles usually have a tyre lifespan of six years, while heavy-duty trucks and buses typically have a lifespan of only three years (Lee et al., 2020). Therefore, we use four years as a representative average lifespan for this study (Hillenbrand et al., 2005). This translates to an annual weight loss rate (L_{mass}) of 2.5 %-7.5 %.

2.2.2. Method 2 (Emission factors)

The second estimation approach is predicated upon specific emission factors (EFs) corresponding to different vehicle types, combined with vehicles kilometers traveled (VKT):

$$E_2 = \sum_{i=1}^n VKT_i \times EF_i \times F_1 (n = 1 \dots 5) \tag{2}$$

where E_2 = the yearly country-based TWP emission using method 2 (kg/year); i = index parameter to identify the vehicle category for which the TWP emission is estimated (i.e., passenger cars, light commercial vehicles, heavy-duty vehicles, buses, and mopeds) (-); VKT_i = the total mileage traveled annually for each vehicle type (km/year); EF_i = the mass of TRWP released per kilometer for each vehicle type (mg/vehicle*km⁻¹); F_1 = the conversion coefficient from TRWP to TWP, with a fixed range between 47 % and 94 % for all vehicle categories (Rødland et al., 2023).

Typically, the EF is derived by placing a vacuum system behind a vehicle tyre to capture TRWP particles using a sampling device (Kreider et al., 2010; Tonegawa and Sasaki, 2021). While such physical sampling systems may have limitations in capturing the smallest nano-sized particles (<100 nm), this is not expected to significantly influence the total mass-based emission factors, as the vast majority of TWP mass is known to be concentrated in coarser particle fractions (>1 µm). EFs for five vehicle categories were gathered from 36 scientific articles and government publications, resulting in a total of 136 EF data points (Fig. S1 in the supplementary information). These categories include passenger cars (N = 50), light commercial vehicles (N = 18), heavy-duty vehicles (N = 29), buses (N = 18), and motorcycles & mopeds (N = 21). Most gathered EFs originate from empirical studies, encompassing both on-road and in-tunnel field measurements as well as laboratory assessments. A smaller subset of EFs was obtained from existing estimation modelling studies. These data were consolidated for the purposes of this study (Fig. 1). For each vehicle category, the minimum, maximum, and average EFs depicted in Fig. 1 were subsequently utilized as separate scenarios to estimate the range of TWP emissions using Method 2.

2.2.3. Method 3 (Thickness loss)

The third method, similar in form to the mass-loss approach (Method 1), instead converts legally mandated tread depth reduction into a mass wear estimate:

$$E_3 = \sum_{i=1}^n N_{tyre,i} \times L_{volume,i} \times F_2 (n = 1 \dots 5) \tag{3}$$

where E_3 = the yearly country-based TWP emission using method 3 (kg/year); i = index parameter to identify the vehicle category for which the TWP emission is estimated (i.e., passenger cars, light commercial vehicles, heavy-duty vehicles, buses, and mopeds) (-); $N_{tyre,i}$ = the total number of tyres for each vehicle type registered in a country (-); $L_{volume,i}$ = the annual volume loss rate of the tyres for each vehicle type (cm³/year); F_2 = the specific gravity of tyre rubber, which is approximately 1.15 (US FHA, 2016) (kg/m³).

In this method, we translate the regulatory end-of-life criterion defined by the Japanese Road Transport Vehicle Law, the requirement that tyres be replaced when tread depth wears from 8 mm to 1.6 mm, into a volumetric wear estimate (and corresponding mass wear estimate) that also aligns with EU inspection standards such as MOT and TÜV. By applying this depth-based reduction to the cross-sectional height and width of tyres across five vehicle categories, Yamashita and Yamanaka (2013) calculated annual volume-loss ranging from 284 cm³ y⁻¹ to 1493 cm³ y⁻¹ (see Table S2), corresponding to an annual mass loss ranging from 0.33 to 1.72 kg y⁻¹ based on a specific gravity of 1.15.

2.3. Pathways to surface water

TWP emitted into the environment through mechanical abrasion is subject to diverse transport pathways. To obtain a broad applicability for the distribution of TWP transport pathways across EU countries, the findings from existing literature concerning the fate and flow of TWP in the environment were collected and analyzed (detailed in Table S3). Only a minor fraction of TWP is expected to be emitted into the atmosphere. Based on a review of existing literature, which shows values ranging from 0.1 % to 15 % (Table S3a), we adopted a representative value of 5 % for our model. The remaining portions are likely to reach nearby road soils, enter surface waters directly via runoff, and pass through wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). The efficiency of these WWTPs in treating wastewater determines how much of the TWP ultimately reaches surface waters. In the present study, transport pathways are categorized based on different environmental compartments, drawing references from Hann et al. (2016) and Deltares and TNO (2024). These studies were selected because they offer detailed categorizations suitable for EU contexts, providing clear distinctions between urban, rural, and highway road types.

As depicted in Table 1, urban roads are generally connected to sewer systems designed to collect street runoff, and therefore it is estimated that 57 % of TWP from urban roads will enter sewer systems, while the remaining portion is likely to be washed into roadside soils and consequently deposited (Hann et al., 2016; Deltares and TNO, 2024). The average proportion of the population connected to WWTPs in each country, along with the average retention rate of these plants, is summarized in Table S4. Conversely, for TWP originating from rural and highway roads, which typically lack connections to sewer systems, around 85.5 % of TWP is expected to remain in the adjacent soils, with the remaining 9.5 % directly transported to surface waters (Hann et al., 2016; Deltares and TNO, 2024). The share of road length in each road class for each EU Member State is given in Table S5.

2.4. TWP emission prediction model

Based on the estimated TWP emissions of EU member states we created a predictive framework for TWP emissions. We developed and compared two distinct modeling approaches using country-level socio-economic and infrastructural data as predictors.

2.4.1. Demographic variables

TWP emissions are influenced by demographic variables such as

Fig. 1. Vehicle-specific emission factors of TRWP (mg/vehicle*km⁻¹) collect from 36 publications (N = 136). MOP = Motorcycle & Mopeds, PC = Passenger cars, LCV = Light commercial vehicles, BUS = buses, HDV = Heavy duty vehicles. Note: These EFs represent total particle mass emissions, not specific fine fractions like PM₁₀ or PM_{2.5}.

Table 1
Parameters and assumptions applied to calculate TWP emissions for each EU member states and its distribution in the environment.

Parameter related to TWP emission	Data applied	Unit	Comments	Reference
Emission factors	Mean per vehicle category (See Fig. S1 for details)	mg/vkm ⁻¹	Vehicle type-specific: MOP, PC, LCV, BUS and HDV	Data collected from 36 publications
Annual weight loss rate	2.5–7.5	%/y	Tyre weight loss ranges from 10 %-30 % over a 4 years lifespan	Data collected from 14 publications Detailed information in Table S1
Annual volume loss rate	284–1493	cm ³ /y	Volume loss ranges from 1135-5973 cm ³ over a 4 years lifespan	Yamashita and Yamanaka (2013)
Country-specific data	Data applied	Unit	Comments	Reference
Road length (different road types)	Road length type specific per capita per EU member states	km/cap	Details provided in Table S5	European Commission (2022)
Number of vehicle registrations	See Table S6	total number	Vehicle type-specific per EU member state	National statistics database
Total mileage per year	See Table S7	x10 ⁶ km/y	Total vehicle kilometers traveled per vehicle type per EU member state	National statistics database
TWP emission pathway	Urban road	Rural road and Highway	Unit	Comments
Air	5 % 5 %	Mass %	Details provided in Table S3a	(Hann et al., 2016; Deltares and TNO, 2024)
Soil	38 %	85.5 %	Mass %	(Hann et al., 2016; Deltares and TNO, 2024)
Surface water	–	9.5 %	Mass %	(Hann et al., 2016; Deltares and TNO, 2024)
Sewers	57 %	–	Mass %	(Hann et al., 2016; Deltares and TNO, 2024)
Removal efficiency	Data applied	Unit	Comments	Reference
Removal efficiency from wastewater for each EU member state	See Table S4	Mass %	Refers to proportion of population covered by WWTP and estimated average microplastic retention rates per EU member state	(Hann et al., 2016)

vehicle travel distance, the number of registered vehicles, and road driving conditions. Beyond these primary variables, TWP emissions may also correlate with a nation’s level of economic development and the status of its transportation infrastructure (Chen et al., 2023; Wagner et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2023). The demographic variables that were included in the present study were identified through literature review. Available national-level data on these demographic variables were sourced from multiple authoritative databases, including the World Bank Group, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and official national statistical repositories.

2.4.2. Modeling approaches

We employed a dual-modeling strategy to balance interpretability and predictive accuracy, developing separate emission prediction models for distinct vehicle categories and geographic scopes. Specifically, four vehicle-specific emission models (i.e., for passenger cars, trucks, buses and motorcycles respectively) and one region-specific model for the European Union (EU) were constructed.

(a) Interpretable linear model (OLS)

We first developed multivariate Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression models based on the general form:

$$EP_i = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_{ij} \times PF_{ij} + \varepsilon_0 (i = 1 \dots 6 \text{ and } n = 1 \dots 11) \tag{4}$$

where EP_i = the yearly predictive per capita TWP emission (kg/year*capita); i = index parameter to identify the vehicle category for which the TWP emission is estimated (i.e., passenger cars, light commercial vehicles, heavy-duty vehicles, buses, and mopeds) (-); β_0 = the intercept (-); β_{ij} = the regression coefficients corresponding to each predictor (-);

$PF_{i,j}$ = the standardized results of each explanatory variable across different countries (-); ε_0 = the random error (-).

For the EU-level OLS model, emission data inputs were generated by averaging emission estimates derived from three independent methodologies documented in previous literature, thereby enhancing robustness (Baensch-Baltruschat et al., 2020; Unice et al., 2019; Kole et al., 2017). The EU-OLS model utilized datasets from all 27 EU member countries (N = 27). For vehicle-specific models, data were lacking due to missing vehicle-disaggregated data in certain countries (N = 24 for PC, TRUCK, and MOP; N = 22 for BUS). A detailed country-by-model data availability matrix is provided in Supplementary Table S3. The optimal predictor variables for each OLS model were determined using a backward stepwise selection approach guided by the corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AICc), accounting for the limited sample size (Akaike, 1974; Anderson and Burnham, 2002). Model selection and AICc calculations were conducted using the *MuMin* package in RStudio.

(b) Random Forest (RF) Model

Recognizing that real-world relationships are often complex, we also developed a non-parametric RF model for each emission category. RF is a powerful machine learning algorithm that constructs an ensemble of decision trees to capture complex non-linear relationships and variable interactions without relying on the strict assumptions of linear regression. Each RF model was built using 500 trees (ntree = 500), a standard practice to ensure stable results.

2.4.3. Model validation and statistical analysis

A thorough validation framework was applied to ensure the robustness of our models. All statistical analyses were performed using RStudio (version 4.2.1, 2020). (1) OLS Model Diagnostics: The validity of the OLS models was contingent on meeting several statistical assumptions.

We formally tested for multicollinearity using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) with the *car* package (Fox and Weisberg, 2018), ensuring all VIF values remained below the conservative threshold of 3 (Table S11). Furthermore, we conducted a comprehensive diagnostic analysis of the model residuals to check for linearity, homoscedasticity, and normality using standard diagnostic plots (Figs. S4-S8). (2) Predictive Performance Evaluation: The generalization ability of both OLS and RF models was thoroughly evaluated using metrics derived from a Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation (LOOCV) procedure. We report three key metrics (Table S14): the LOOCV-based coefficient of determination (R^2), normalized root-mean-square error (nRMSE), and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE). (3) RF Model Interpretability: To gain insights from the RF models, we employed two standard techniques using the *randomForest* and *pdp* packages. Variable Importance was quantified by the percentage increase in mean squared error (%IncMSE) upon permutation of each predictor. Partial Dependence Plots (PDPs) were generated to visualize the marginal effect of the most important predictors on the predicted outcome (Fig. S10).

3. Results

3.1. Comparative analysis of TWP emission estimation methods

Fig. 2 illustrates the average per capita TWP emission in each of the 27 EU member states and their associated countries, using each of the three emission estimation methods extracted from literature (Sections 2.2.1–2.2.3). The emission estimates show considerable variation. Nearly all data points representing national TWP emissions reported in literature (subjected to unit conversion for comparative analysis) are contained within the estimated emission ranges.

When focusing on the comparison among the maximum results derived from these three methods, it can be observed that nearly all Southern and Eastern European countries, as well as Estonia and Finland from Northern Europe, exhibit significantly higher per capita emissions when estimated based on mass loss of tyres (Method 1), compared to the results obtained from the remaining two methods. Particularly, the results for Greece and Malta, where the discrepancies in per capita TWP emissions are pronounced when comparing the maximum estimated values from mass loss of tyres (Method 1) to those from EF estimations (Method 2). For Greece, the maximum emission estimated by Method 1 is 4.81 kg/y*cap, whereas Method 2 estimates only 2.07 kg/y*cap, indicating that Method 1 yields a result approximately 2.3 times higher than Method 2 (Table S13). Similarly, for Malta, the maximum emission using Method 1 is about 1.97 times higher than the Method 2 estimation. Interestingly, an opposite trend is observed in Western European countries. The per capita TWP emissions estimated using an EF (Method 2) are slightly higher than those calculated based on weight loss (Method 1). For Germany and France, the discrepancies between the results obtained from these two methods are particularly small, i.e., merely 0.1 and 0.2 kg/y*cap, respectively. Distinct from the first two approaches, the per capita TWP emissions estimated based on thickness loss of tyres (Method 3) are generally situated around the mean values of the results obtained from the other two methods across nearly all EU member states.

3.2. Regional distribution of vehicle-specific TWP emissions

Fig. 3 illustrates the comparison between per capita TWP emissions from passenger cars (PC) and trucks (LCV and HDV) across the 27 EU member states. The analysis highlights significant differences in the primary sources of emissions among these countries. Passenger cars dominate TWP emissions in Western European countries, often accounting for more than half of the total emissions. Conversely, in several Northern and Southern European countries, trucks emerge as the major contributors, representing >60 % of total emissions. For instance, Greece and Malta have particularly high proportions of truck-related

emissions, with passenger cars contributing only 27 % and 36 %, respectively. Detailed data for all vehicle categories, including buses and motorcycles, can be found in Fig. S7 in the supplementary information. Notably, the emissions from buses and motorcycles constitute relatively minor fractions across all EU countries, typically around 1 % and up to 8 %, respectively, indicating their lesser overall impact on national TWP emission profiles.

3.3. TWP emissions reaching surface waters

Fig. 4 reveals the mean TWP emissions derived from three different estimation methods, distinguishing between total emissions generated (A) and those entering surface waters across EU member states (B). Regardless of wastewater treatment, Germany, France, Italy, Spain, and Poland consistently exhibit the highest annual TWP emissions (amount generated and amount reaching surface waters) among EU member states. The amount of TWP generated by Germany, France, and Italy exceeds 100,000 tons, with respective values of 137,000 tons, 116,000 tons, and 105,000 tons. In contrast, for the amount of TWP entering surface waters, Germany ranks third in total mass, while Italy and France are the top two contributors, each annually introducing nearly 14,000 tons of TWP into surface waters.

3.4. Correlation between demographic variables and TWP emissions and comparison of model performances

This section delves into the impact of various demographic factors on TWP emissions, using Pearson's correlation analysis to explore relationships between TWP emissions and eleven identified demographic variables (Fig. 5). These variables include Gross Domestic Product (GDP), total road length, total length of highways, secondary roads, local roads and all paved roads, the number of vehicles in use, urban road performance,¹ overall road performance, freight volume, and gasoline prices. Pearson's correlation analysis (Fig. S2) revealed several important associations; for instance, total per capita emissions correlated positively with Road Freight Transport (RFT), while passenger car emissions were most strongly associated with GDP and road performance.

The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) models, built upon preliminary insights, confirmed several hypothesized relationships. As shown in the coefficient analysis (Table S12), both GDP and RFT were significant positive predictors for total per capita emissions, with standardized unit increases in GDP and RFT corresponding to average emission increases of 0.28 kg/cap · y and 0.29 kg/cap · y, respectively ($p < 0.05$). Models for other vehicle categories successfully identified statistically significant drivers, such as the negative association between gasoline prices and bus emissions, and the complex relationships between road performance and moped emissions.

The Random Forest (RF) models consistently outperformed their OLS counterparts across all evaluation metrics. For the critical TOTAL model, the Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation (LOOCV) R^2 improved markedly from 0.531 (OLS) to 0.846 (RF), and the nRMSE decreased from a "Reliable" 26.5 % to a "Good" 14.8 % (Table S14). This substantial improvement in predictive capability is visually demonstrated by the tighter clustering of RF predictions (in red) around the 1:1 line of perfect agreement, compared to the OLS predictions (in blue) in the Observed vs. Predicted plots (Fig. S9).

The variable importance analysis (left panel of Fig. S10) validated findings from the linear models, clearly confirming that RFT is the most critical predictor for both TOTAL and TRUCK emissions. Critically,

¹ Road performance is based on an accessibility framework developed by the European Commission, International Transport Forum, and Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (ITF), relying on three key indicators: accessibility, proximity, and transport performance.

Fig. 2. Per capita emissions of tyre wear particles (TWP) in kg/year*cap for each EU Member State calculated using three distinct method. Bars represent the ranges of estimates from these three calculation methods for each country. Literature data points (symbols) depict previously published measured or estimated values from various sources for comparative purposes.

Fig. 3. The distribution of per capita TWP emissions from various vehicle types across distinct countries is analyzed with reference to specific European regions. (Results based on the mean value of the three estimation methods; please note scales vary by vehicle type).

Partial Dependence Plots (PDPs) revealed pronounced non-linear features underlying the differences in model performance. For example, the PDP illustrating the effect of RFT on TOTAL emissions (right panel of Fig. S10) demonstrated a distinct saturating trend: the positive impact of RFT on emissions is strong at lower levels but significantly diminishes as RFT increases.

3.5. Global projection of TWP emissions

To provide a preliminary global outlook, we applied our Random Forest (RF) modeling framework to a dataset of 57 countries. The model predicts both per capita emissions and their associated uncertainty (see Table S16 for full results), revealing significant global disparities as

illustrated in per capita emission analysis categorized by continent (Fig. 6) and total national emissions map (Fig. 7).

The analysis highlights a clear divide in per capita emissions. Most countries in Asia, Africa, and South America are predicted to have emissions below 1.5 kg/cap*y. In contrast, developed nations in Europe and North America show significantly higher levels. Luxembourg emerges as the global leader with a predicted emission of 3.56 (±0.35) kg/cap*y, followed by the United States at 3.12 (±0.32) kg/cap*y, and other high-income nations like Switzerland (2.95 kg/cap*y) and Norway (2.89 kg/cap*y). Oceania exhibits levels comparable to developed European countries.

When considering total national emissions, population size becomes the dominant factor. China is projected to have the highest total annual

Fig. 4. (A) Geographic distribution of annual TWP emissions generated by vehicles (t/y); (B) Geographic distribution of annual TWP emissions entering the surface water (t/y).

Fig. 5. Pearson correlations for all car types (TOTAL), passenger cars (PC), light commercial and heavy-duty vehicles (Trucks), buses (BUS), motorcycles and mopeds (MOD), as well as the main affecting factors. The size of each circle represents the strength of the correlation, with larger circles indicating stronger correlations. Positive correlations are indicated in (higher shades of) red, while negative correlations are indicated in (higher shades of) blue. Statistically significant correlations are denoted by ***p-value < 0.001, **p-value < 0.01, and *p-value < 0.05.

Fig. 6. Distribution of predicted per capita TWP emission worldwide (kg/cap*y) (Fig. S6 with country abbreviations).

Fig. 7. Distribution of predicted total annual TWP emission worldwide (t/y) (Fig. S7 with country abbreviations).

emissions at approximately 1.5 million tons, followed by the United States (1.04 million tons) and India (870,000 tons). Brazil also emerges as a major contributor with around 260,000 tons annually. In contrast, most nations in Africa and Oceania, due to smaller populations and lower per capita emissions, contribute a relatively smaller share to the global total emissions.

4. Discussion

4.1. Evaluating methodological variability and its implications

Fig. 2 illustrates that per capita TWP emissions estimated by Method 1 (mass loss) are typically higher than those derived via Method 2 (emission factors). This tendency is confirmed by other scholars, including Menekes and Nowack (2022). Detailed examination of the key determinants of the emission equations (Section 2.2), notably loss

rates (either weight or thickness), annual average mileage, and the EFs, provides insight into the variability characterizing each method. The inflated emission estimates associated with Method 1 (weight loss) could be due to an overestimation of mass loss rates of tyres. However, other studies, e.g., [Mennekes and Nowack \(2022\)](#) and [Prenner et al. \(2021\)](#), propose a loss of less than 20 %, resulting an annual mass loss rate of 5 % instead of 7.5 %. Conversely, Method 2 relies on empirical emission factors (EFs) and mileage data, rendering it highly sensitive to the quality and variability of both. For instance, the disparity in EFs is minimal for passenger vehicles and motorcycles but is pronounced for trucks, with the difference between maximum and minimum values for both light and heavy-duty trucks reaching 700–800 mg/km, exerting a substantial impact on the results ([Figs. 1 and S1](#)). Moreover, EU member states' vehicle mileage data, though largely drawn from official national statistics, are neither fully standardized nor harmonized, introducing additional uncertainties.

Method 3 (thickness loss) yields results that approximate the mean values derived from the aforementioned two methods. This trend potentially underscores the efficacy of thickness loss as a reliable evaluative metric, illuminating a balanced approach among the comparative analysis of diverse methodologies. However, limited research on the loss of tyre thickness measurement suggests that the uncertainties associated with this method are not yet fully understood, necessitating a cautious interpretation of these results. Moreover, the methodology based on weight/thickness loss rates does not account for international transport which can be relevant for countries receiving a lot of international transport or having a large international transportation sector ([Prenner et al., 2021](#); [Wagner et al., 2018](#)). This oversight disproportionately affects small countries, like Austria, where the notable amount of incoming foreign traffic likely results in an overestimation of national tyre loss estimates. Therefore, the imbalance between incoming foreign traffic and outgoing national traffic affects the magnification of inaccuracies in tyre loss estimations.

Beyond these foundational differences in how each method represents tyre or vehicle usage, numerous additional factors, such as driving style (e.g., aggressive vs. moderate), road and landscape conditions (pavement quality, slope, curvature), vehicle load, and tyre composition, can markedly influence TWP release. In this study, which focuses on national-scale assessments across EU member states, we unavoidably simplify these variables. However, if the goal of a future study were to model TWP with finer spatial or temporal resolution, then more detailed metrics, such as the proportion of urban, highway, or mountainous driving would become essential.

In general, each of the three methods has its strengths and limitations. Therefore, employing all three approaches concurrently to estimate the TWP emissions of a specific country will result in a comprehensive range of emission values. For Western European countries, the disparities in results derived from these methods are not pronounced. For countries with substantial international or cross-border transportation, Method 2, which is based on vehicle kilometers traveled, may provide more realistic estimates compared to Methods 1 or 3. For other European nations, where significant variability in outcomes is observed due to methodological differences, the implementation of multiple techniques is recommended to reach a more thorough insight.

4.2. Differential impact by vehicle types on national emission profiles

In [Section 4.1](#), we observed that per capita TWP emissions estimated using Method 1 (mass loss) are generally higher than those estimated using Method 2 (emission factors), with significant discrepancies in countries such as Greece and Malta, as illustrated in [Fig. 2](#). This disparity is partly due to the higher tyre loss rates assumed by Method 1. Extensive analysis of vehicle-specific emission contributions, as shown in [Fig. 3](#), indicates that in these countries, trucks account for over 60 % of total emissions. This considerable share of truck emissions is essential because trucks possess larger and more numerous tyres, inherently

leading to higher emissions. Moreover, data suggest a relatively high per capita ownership of trucks in these nations, intensifying this emission trend. This analysis indirectly explains why per capita TWP emissions derived from Method 1 are elevated in these regions. In contrast, the disparity between the methods in Western European countries is minimal, primarily attributed to the larger proportion of passenger cars and the smaller variability in emission factors for passenger cars. Across all EU regions, emissions from buses and mopeds make a negligible contribution to the overall TWP emissions, whereas emissions from passenger cars and trucks significantly dominate the emission profiles, markedly influencing the TWP levels on a national scale.

Furthermore, the disproportionate emissions from trucks observed in some countries reflect not only domestic activities but also the transnational nature of truck operations. Many trucks in these regions engage in extensive cross-border transportation, which complicates emission estimations. This complexity highlights the tricky factors influencing TWP emissions, which include not just vehicle counts but also economic activities like international trade. Additionally, economic factors such as GDP per capita significantly influence emission patterns, which will be further discussed in subsequent sections ([Section 4.4](#)). Thus, current estimation methodologies may be insufficient as they often fail to fully account for the impacts of international transport.

To improve the truthfulness of these estimations, particularly for international transport, it would be beneficial to distinguish between domestic and cross-border vehicle types and mileage. For instance, mileage from cross-border trucks could be independently tracked and assessed regularly instead of being aggregated into the total domestic mileage. Furthermore, incorporating additional influencing factors into current estimation methods (i.e., cargo transport volumes), especially for countries heavily reliant on international road transport, could refine these estimates. This detailed approach would help clarify how various vehicle types, especially trucks, disproportionately impact national emission profiles due to their operational and economic contexts.

4.3. Impacts of wastewater treatment variability on TWP discharge into surface waters

The variability in TWP emissions into surface waters, as depicted in [Fig. 4](#), largely depends on the efficiency of wastewater treatment facilities across different EU member states. Germany exemplifies high-efficiency wastewater management, connecting 93 % of its population to tertiary treatment facilities with an 84 % removal efficiency. This is closely followed by the Netherlands, which achieves an 86 % efficiency rate. In contrast, France and Italy exhibit lower efficiencies at 62 % and 48 %, respectively, resulting in higher discharges of tyre wear particles into surface waters ([Table S4](#)). The regional discharge rates into surface waters reflect these efficiencies: Western European countries, on average, discharge 10 % of their total TWP, with the Netherlands reporting the lowest at 9 %. Eastern European countries see a higher discharge rate averaging 13 %, with Romania experiencing the highest at 15 %. Overall, this study's findings indicate that TWP emissions entering surface waters across EU member states vary from 9 % to 15 %.

These findings align with recent studies, such as those by [Lassen et al. \(2015\)](#), [Unice et al. \(2019\)](#), and [Wagner et al. \(2018\)](#), which have similarly estimated the annual release of tyre wear into surface waters. [Baensch-Baltruschat et al. \(2020\)](#) conducted a comprehensive assessment across the German road system, accounting for the effects of different wastewater treatment systems and varying road types, finding that approximately 12 %–20 % of tyre particles are released into surface waters. Comparable studies focusing on the Netherlands by [Kole et al. \(2015\)](#) and [Verschoor et al. \(2016\)](#) suggest a release range of 6 %–11 %, corroborating the trends observed in our study.

However, the methodology employed in this study prioritizes broad applicability across EU states by mainly considering urban roads connected to WWTPs. This simplification may not capture the complexities of some highways in developed regions equipped with advanced

technical drainage systems that mitigate direct runoff into surface waters. Given these complexities, while this study establishes a baseline understanding, it emphasizes the need for detailed, country-specific research to refine the environmental pathways of TWP emissions. It is also crucial to acknowledge a major source of uncertainty in our pathway analysis: the exclusion of Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs). The cumulative national discharge of untreated TWP during wet weather events could be substantial, but this pathway cannot be robustly modeled at a pan-European scale due to a critical lack of data on CSO frequency and overflow volumes across member states.

4.4. Role of socioeconomic and infrastructural variables in TWP emissions

Our analysis highlights pronounced regional disparities in per capita TWP emissions across the EU, emphasizing the importance of location-specific emission drivers (Fig. 2). Western European countries generally exhibit consistent emission profiles dominated by passenger car (PC) emissions, often surpassing 50 % of total TWP emissions (Fig. 3). Our Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression confirms a statistically significant positive correlation between these emissions, GDP, and road performance indicators (Table S12).

In contrast, Southern, Northern, and Baltic European states display higher and more variable per capita emissions primarily driven by truck traffic (LCV & HDV), exceeding 60 % of total emissions in countries like Greece, Malta, and Latvia. This suggests freight transport rather than general economic prosperity is the key driver in these regions. The Random Forest (RF) model further reinforces this finding by identifying road freight transport (RFT) as the predominant predictor of emissions in truck-dominated countries (Fig. S10), independently corroborated by OLS results. These countries' elevated emissions thus reflect their strategic roles as logistical hubs within Europe. Critically, our RF analysis reveals a non-linear, saturating relationship between RFT and emissions (Fig. S10). This indicates that incremental increases in freight volume in countries already operating at high capacities yield progressively smaller increases in emissions, highlighting the growing importance of other factors, such as vehicle technology and road quality.

These findings hold substantial policy implications tailored to regional emission drivers. In Western Europe, effective mitigation strategies should focus on addressing the systemic factors driving high passenger car usage, such as integrated urban development and improved public transportation infrastructure. For Southern, Northern, and Baltic states with predominant truck-related emissions, policy interventions should address the identified non-linear RFT-emission relationship by focusing on enhancing vehicle efficiency (e.g., promoting low-wear tires) and investing in advanced, low-abrasion road surfacing technologies on major freight corridors. Our dual-model approach thus not only elucidates regional emission patterns but also provides actionable insights to guide targeted, context-specific environmental policy decisions.

4.5. Global TWP emissions

The top-ranking per capita TWP emissions of Luxembourg can be mainly attributed to it having the world's highest GDP per capita and a relatively extensive transportation sector (Fig. 6). Conversely, in the United States, high per capita emissions are not only due to its ranking as eighth globally in GDP per capita. Rather, they are significantly influenced by a high number of vehicles per capita and an extensive road network, factors that combine to make the U.S. rank second in per capita emissions. In contrast, China, another major global economy, records per capita emissions of approximately 1 kg/cap*y, lower than the global average. This lower figure results from China's below-average per capita GDP and vehicle ownership numbers. Overall, data from the global-specific model indicate that per capita TWP emissions are primarily driven by GDP per capita and per capita road freight transport volume.

Additionally, road length and vehicle ownership numbers also influence the outcomes.

In our analysis, substantial regional variations in annual total TWP emissions are evident (Fig. 7). Although China and India exhibit lower per capita TWP emissions, their large populations drive their annual emissions to considerable levels, with figures reaching 1,500,000 and 870,000 tons respectively. In contrast, the United States, with the second-highest per capita TWP emissions globally, also presents substantial national emissions, totaling nearly 1,040,000 tons annually. This highlights how both per capita emissions and population sizes contribute to national totals. Meanwhile, in Europe, countries typically exhibit higher per capita emissions than those in African and Asian regions; however, their relatively smaller populations mean that total emissions remain lower than those observed in more populous regions of Asia and Africa.

Comparing the total national emission figures from this study with estimates from other publications, it is apparent that available comparative data is limited. This raises a concern: most current studies focus primarily on TWP emissions within Europe, with few studies addressing emissions outside of Europe (Councell et al., 2004; Kole et al., 2017; Zhou et al., 2023). Notably, studies like those by Moran et al. (2023) in the U.S. still rely on emission factors derived from European data, further emphasizing the scarcity of empirical data outside Europe.

Table 2 presents a comparative analysis of representative countries from each continent, comparing literature-reported per capita TWP emissions against those estimated by our OLS model and RF model. Most notably, the literature values generally align closely with the model outputs. However, exceptions exist, such as the estimates by Kole et al. (2017) for the U.S., which are slightly higher than our model's predictions because they employed fixed EFs for heavy duty vehicles, remarkably much higher than the average values. Furthermore, Kole et al. (2017) estimated annual TWP emissions for China and India at 756,000 tons and 293,000 tons respectively, figures that significantly diverge from ours. This discrepancy may be attributed to their reliance on outdated data concerning vehicle registrations and annual mileage, potentially leading to underestimations of actual emissions. Conversely, Zhou et al. (2023) used more recent data to estimate China's tyre emissions at approximately 1,560,000 tons annually, aligning closely with our estimate of 1,500,000 tons. These findings highlight the critical impact of utilizing current and comprehensive data in TWP emission estimations, stressing the need for updated and region-specific methodologies to achieve more truthful global emission profiles.

4.6. Strengths, limitations, and potential further work

A key strength of this study is its rigorous, multi-layered methodological framework. By first comparing three distinct literature-based estimation methods across the EU, we established a robust, uncertainty-aware baseline for TWP emissions. More significantly, we then developed a novel dual-modeling approach, contrasting an interpretable Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) model with a high-performance Random Forest (RF) model. This innovative use of machine learning not only provided a more accurate and scalable tool for global emission projections but also, through their comparison, yielded a fundamental insight: the drivers of TWP emissions are inherently non-linear. This methodological contribution itself offers guidance for future large-scale environmental modeling. Our work provides preliminary, data-driven emission estimates for data-scarce regions, emphasizing the global scale of the TWP challenge and catalyzing targeted research.

The primary limitation of our study remains the extrapolation of a model trained on EU data to other geographic regions. While our RF model uses globally applicable socioeconomic predictors, it cannot capture unique regional factors that may significantly alter emission rates. For instance, poorer road conditions in some developing nations, or different dominant vehicle technologies, are sources of uncertainty not accounted for in our model. A second significant constraint is the

Table 2

Comparison of the estimated per capita TWP emissions for each representative country in each continent in the literature with the values obtained in this study using the OLS model and RF model.

Continent	Country	Source	Estimated per capita TWP emissions (kg/cap*y)	Method used (EF: Emission factor)	
North America	The United States	Moran et al., 2023	1.9–3.0	EF and Mass Loss	
		United States Federal Highway Administration, 2016	2.1	Mass loss	
		Council et al., 2004	3.0–3.4	EF and Mass Loss	
		Kole et al., 2017	3.8–5.5	EF and Mass Loss	
		Wagner et al., 2018	3.4	EF	
	Canada	This study	2.4–3.8	OLS model	
		Mian et al., 2022	2.8–3.4	RF model	
		This study	0.4–2.9	EF	
		This study	1.0–2.8	OLS model	
		This study	2.3–2.8	RF model	
South America	Brazil	Goehler et al., 2022	0.4–1.9	EF	
		Kole et al., 2017	1.4	EF	
		This study	0.8–1.6	OLS model	
Europe	Western Europe	Germany	This study	1.1–1.4	RF model
			Baensch-Baltruschat et al., 2020	0.9–1.2	EF
			Kole et al., 2017	1.5	EF
			Wagner et al., 2018	1.7	EF
			Chen et al., 2023	1.1–2.3	EF
	Northern Europe	Sweden	This study	1.5–2.0	OLS model
			Polukarova et al., 2024	1.1	RF model
			Magnusson et al., 2016	1.3	EF and Mass Loss
			This study	0.9–2.4	EF
			This study	0.9–2.4	OLS model
Eastern Europe	Poland	This study	1.6–1.7	RF model	
		Chen et al., 2023	1.3–2.7	EF	
		This study	1.8–2.1	OLS model	
Southern Europe	Italy	This study	1.8–2.1	RF model	
		Kole et al., 2017	0.9	Mass loss	
		Chen et al., 2023	1.3–2.2	EF	
Asia	Japan	This study	1.2–1.4	RF model	
		Ono et al., 2023	0.5–1.4	EF	
		Kole et al., 2017	1.9	Tyre thickness Loss	
		This study	1.0–1.7	OLS model	
		This study	1.8–2.3	RF model	
	Korea		Lee et al., 2020	1.0–1.1	EF
			This study	0.7–1.6	OLS model
			This study	1.7–2.1	RF model
	India		Kole et al., 2017	0.2	EF
			Chen et al., 2023	0.5	EF

Table 2 (continued)

Continent	Country	Source	Estimated per capita TWP emissions (kg/cap*y)	Method used (EF: Emission factor)		
	China	This study	0.04–1.2	OLS model		
		This study	1.0–1.5	RF model		
		Zhou et al., 2023	1.0	EF		
		Kole et al., 2017	0.6	EF		
		This study	0.6–1.5	OLS model		
		This study	1.4–1.8	RF model		
		Oceania	Australia	Milani et al., 2004	0.9	Unknown
				This study	1.1–2.8	OLS model
		This study	1.9–2.4	RF model		

underlying scarcity and variability of empirical tyre wear measurement data, which predominantly originates from European studies. This introduces uncertainty into our training data and highlights the challenge of applying findings globally. Lastly, our model does not incorporate driving behavior, and the prevalence of aggressive driving styles in certain regions could lead to an underestimation of actual TWP emissions. A further key limitation is the exclusion of Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs) from our environmental pathway analysis. Due to a lack of consistent, national-level data on overflow frequency and volume, we were unable to quantify this potentially significant pathway for direct TWP release to surface waters.“

Future research should prioritize several key areas to build upon this work. The most critical need is the collection of localized emission data from non-European regions, particularly Asia, Africa, and South America. Developing region-specific emission factors through harmonized field studies would be invaluable for training and validating more accurate, regionally-calibrated models. Furthermore, future modeling efforts could incorporate additional predictor variables, such as climate data (e.g., temperature and precipitation), road surface type distribution, and indicators of traffic congestion. Such advancements would not only refine global emission estimates but also enable more targeted and effective policy interventions, providing a clearer picture of the world-wide impact of TWP on environmental health.

5. Conclusion

To estimate TWP emissions for EU member states, this study used three methods extracted from the literature. It reveals large discrepancies between methods, potentially due to overestimations of tyre mass loss over their lifespans and substantial variability in EFs across different vehicle types. The imbalance between foreign incoming and domestic outgoing traffic in smaller countries like Malta also contributes to the uncertainty in national TWP estimations.

By integrating the transport pathways of TWP in the environment, the study estimated both the total TWP generated by vehicles and the emissions entering surface waters. Germany showed the highest total TWP generation, while Italy ended up having the highest TWP levels entering surface waters. This difference can be attributed the higher wastewater treatment connectivity and efficacy in Germany. On average, about 9 %–15 % of TWP emissions across EU member states enter surface waters.

Our comparative analysis, which averaged per capita TWP emissions derived from literature-based estimation methods, confirmed that countries with higher per capita TWP emissions, notably those in the Baltic states, also exhibit higher truck emissions. This analysis focused

on domestic transportation emissions due to the limitation of the estimation methods, which did not capture international freight dynamics. Further correlation studies using these averaged results as inputs have demonstrated that truck TWP emissions are positively correlated with per capita freight volume, road length, and car ownership. These results show that per capita TWP emissions are influenced by a range of demographic factors, rather than a single variable. A key innovation of this study was the development of a dual-modeling framework. While a simple Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) model provided interpretable linear relationships, a more advanced Random Forest (RF) model demonstrated vastly superior predictive accuracy ($LOOCV R^2 > 0.7$) and revealed the complex, non-linear nature of these drivers. This approach simplifies the estimation process using accessible demographic parameters and provides a more robust foundation for global extrapolation, filling the data gap in TWP emissions research outside of Europe.

The primary limitation identified in this study pertains to the inherent uncertainties associated with the used estimation methods and predictive models. This reflection emphasizes the imperative for ongoing research to improve the reliability of these frameworks. Given the considerable variability in emission factors among different vehicle types and driving conditions across various countries, targeted empirical studies are crucial. Such investigations would not only facilitate the development and implementation of region- and vehicle-specific strategies to reduce TWP emissions but also advance our comprehension of the dynamics underlying TWP pollution and emissions.

6. Note

The views and opinions expressed here reflect only the authors' views, and not necessarily those of the European Commission nor the European Research Executive Agency (REA).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Yichen Sun: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jikke van Wijnen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Ad M.J. Ragas:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Yichen Sun reports financial support was provided by European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2025.109720>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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